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Synthesis and anti-bacterial evaluation of novel thio- and oxazepino[7,6-b]quinolones

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Abstract

Cyclocondensation of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes and 2-thiophenol/2-aminophenols led to the formation of benzo[2,3][1,4]thio- or oxazepino[7,6-b]quinolines. Ugi reaction of the latter compound with various carboxylic acids and isocyanides gave novel oxazepino[7,6-b]quinoline derivatives. All compounds were evaluated for their anti-bacterial and anti-fungal activities. Among them, compounds 4a, 4b and 4d showed moderate to good activity.

Keywords

Anti-bacterial, Isocyanide, Oxazepinoquinolines, Thiazepinoquinolines, Ugi condensation.